

Impact of climate change on the coastal natural resources of Bangladesh: Mitigation strategies

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Abstract

The study aims to assess the impact of climate change on the coastal natural resources of Bangladesh. Both primary and secondary data were used to identify the natural resources and the adverse effect of climate change on them. It was found that the dune vegetation is highly impacted by frequent tropical cyclones like *Sidr*, *Nargis*, *Bijli*, *Aila* and *Mahashen*. The highly affected areas became unsuitable for habitation till 2020. The brackish water from the Bay of Bengal is invading freshwater bodies percolating deep into the soil. The increasing trend of salinity disrupts the migration routes contributing to the decreasing trend of *Hilsha* abundance. The respondents opined that declining trends in both *Nypa* palm and mangrove date palm were observed in the littoral areas. The number of climate refugees is increasing day by day. It was noted that Bengal Tigers have been suffering from various diseases by drinking saline water, which eventually affects the normal behaviour of this big cat. The study recommended several mitigation measures: preparing a risk atlas, ecosystem-based solutions, climate-resilient livelihoods through community engagements, process-based modelling of agroforestry in saline areas and greening the blue to overcome the challenges.

Keywords: Climate change, natural resources, tropical cyclone, salinity, green the blue, climate refugee, process-based agroforestry, risk atlas

Introduction

Bangladesh is experiencing both predictable and unpredictable climate change impacts every year (Khan 2019, Chowdhury *et al.* 2020; Haque *et al.* 2020; Ali *et al.* 2019; Hasnat *et al.* 2020; Chiba *et al.* 2017; Alam *et al.* 2020; Billah 2018; Dastagir 2015; Rahman 2020; Rahman 2021; Rahman *et al.* 2021; Rahman 2022b). Sea level rise, increased salinity and drought have become very familiar to our country. Most of the rivers of Bangladesh flow from north to south, silting up the mangrove delta and draining into the Bay of Bengal. The mangrove is a transitional territory between the freshwater rivers originating from the Ganges and the Bay of Bengal. Climate change is affecting many countries of the World but Bangladesh is one of the worst hits where a major portion of the population is poor (Assaduzzaman 2020; Islam and Hossain 2020; Hoque *et al.* 2019, Hossain *et al.* 2021; Islam and Rashid 2012; Saha 2016; Uddin and Basak 2012). Climate change poses a high risk to the ecosystems and landmass of coastal Bangladesh. The major threats are high levels of salinity, sedimentation, cyclones, storm surges, water logging and land erosion (Kaiser 2023).

Coastal islands are stores of huge natural resources. The ecosystems are comprised of inland ecosystems, riparian ecosystems, mangrove ecosystems, littoral ecosystems, offshore ecosystems and marine ecosystems (Rahman 2021a; Rahman 2022 a, c). The biodiversity is characterized by flora and fauna of the Sundarbans; seaweeds; coconut trees; screw pine vegetation; elephant cattail; corals; molluscs, oysters, turtles; crabs; freshwater and marine fishes, sea mammals and reptiles; and migratory birds (Rahman 2023 a, b, c, d, e). The study aimed to assess the impact of climate climatic stressors on the natural resources of the coastal areas of Bangladesh.

Methodology

Both primary and secondary data were used for this study. The secondary data were collected from Forest Department. Local people were personally interviewed to identify the flora and fauna. A focus group discussion was done incorporating the respondents from diverse stakeholders. A total of ten key informants were interviewed to find out the mitigation strategy. Content analysis was done to analyze the data.

Impact of climate change

Dune Vegetation

The respondents argued that the dune vegetation is being submerged due to sea level rise. Supercyclones *Sidr*, *Nargis*, *Bijli*, *Aila* and *Mahashen* impacted the coastal islands through three primary mechanisms: wind damage, storm surge, and sedimentation. The highly affected areas became unsuitable for habitation till 2020. Strong winds toppled stems, broke off trunks and defoliated the canopy. Taller stems of littoral forests (shoreline forests) were uprooted and knocked over. Sediments carried by storm surges were deposited on the forest floor as the surge receded, causing plant mortality by interfering with root and soil gas exchange. Storm surges reduced the viability of seeds, seedling germination and seedling recruitment. Many exotic plant species rapidly colonized the devastated areas. The biological invasion suppresses the native vegetation (Rahman 2023f).

Mangrove's vegetation

The respondents opined that saline water is creeping deeper due to frequent cyclones in consecutive years. The present threat coming from increased salinity jeopardizes the *Sundarbans'* ecosystems. Salinity is more devastating than any other parameter in this territory. It is very difficult to manage salinity because of the lasting nature of its effects on terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems. Most of the tree species are seriously affected when salt concentrates within the root zone. The most significant off-site impact of salinity in the *Sundarbans* is the salinization of previous freshwater rivers and canals. The habitats of aquatic flora are also degraded by increased salinity. There are five forest types in the *Sundarbans*: fresh swamp, mixed fresh-brackish swamp, brackish swamp, mangrove scrub and littoral forest. Meanwhile, the fresh swamp has disappeared due to increased salinity. The mixed swamp is being converted into brackish swamp. Most of the brackish swamps have become mangrove scrubs (Rahman 2020, Rahman *et al.* 2021).

The respondents argued that brackish water from the Bay of Bengal is invading freshwater bodies percolating deep into the soil. *Sundari*, the pioneer tree species has been suffering from a 'Top dying' disease with the increase of salinity. A declining trend of the *Sundari* tree is observed in *Dangmari*, *Karamjal*, *Jongra*, *Mora Passur*, *Pashakhali*, *Nandobala*, *Harbouria*, *Choraputia*, *Buddhomari*, *Katakhali*, *Boroitola*, *Jeodhara*, *Amurbunia*, *Gulishakhali*, *Dhansagor*, *Kolomtezi*,

Nangli, Chandpai, Mrigamari, Andharmanik, Tamulbunia, Supoti, Bogi, Mora Bogi, Dumuria, Charkhali, Shapla, Chandeshwar, Shoronkhola, Panirghat, Bhola, Dashervarani and Kochikhali forest areas of the Sundarbans. *Keora (Excoecaria agallocha), Goran (Ceriops decandra) and Gewa (Excoecaria agallocha)* trees are occupying the lost grounds of *Sundari (Heritiera fomes)* tree. One apprehends that after 20 years *Sundari* trees will be almost disappeared from the Sundarbans virtually changing its nomenclature from ‘*Sundarbans*’ to ‘*Keoraban*’!

Littoral vegetation

The coconut tree is highly affected by increased salinity resulting in a small number of nuts, empty nuts or elongated nuts. Salinity has severely affected riparian vegetation because they occupy the lowest parts of the landscape where they get submerged by saline water. *Nypa* palm and mangrove date palm occur most commonly in areas where the mixture of brackish and freshwater flows (Rahman 2023e). Declining trends of both palms have been observed in the littoral areas. The high mortality of screw pine due to increased salinity enhances dune erosion (Rahman 2023a).

Fisheries and wildlife

A strong wind will destroy honey bee colonies causing high mortality. Corals, woodpeckers, sea turtles and parrots will be severely affected. Plant debris impacts wetland ecosystems by lowering oxygen levels in the water. Many ground birds will lose their habitats, nesting and breeding sites. It will cause harmful effects on crocodile and dolphin populations. The increasing trend of jellyfish invasion along the coast is a sign of disorder in the Bay of Bengal's ecosystems (Rahman and Alam 2019). Seaweed, corals and sea algae are struggling to remain alive. Bengal Tigers have been suffering from various diseases by drinking saline water, which eventually affects the normal behaviour of this big cat. Many fish species and crustaceans migrate from marine water to freshwater for spawning and juvenile feeding. During the commencement of the southwest monsoon and consequent flooding of all the rivers, *Hilsha* starts its spawning migration upstream. The increasing trend of salinity disrupts the migration routes contributing to the decreasing trend of *Hilsha* abundance. The loss of spawning, feeding and nursing grounds has a profound influence on the reduction of *the Hilsha* population to the growing frustration of fishermen of *Dubla Island, Supati, Mahipur, Kochikhali, Kotka, Demra Island, Tia Island, Narkelbariya, Hangsharaj, Arpangashiya, Dobayki, Andermanik, Bishkhali, Baleswar,*

Mathbaria and *Pathorghata* during catching season. These migrations of fish hurt the economy of the country.

Human settlements

The respondents argued that natural hazards will force 3.5 million people living on the coasts to migrate forward and inward. Migration is a tool for survival for the vulnerable. Migration for climate change is a long-run disaster because of its unpredictable scale and impact. Rarely do people migrate by choice, but environmental degradation generates forced migration. Sometimes they move towards the sea instead of inland because of their financial crisis. They cannot afford high lands due to high prices, land disputes and scarcities. They are taken captive by natural calamities. Simultaneously erosion of old lands and accretion of new lands occur. Newly accreted islands welcome homeless and landless people to live and enjoy natural resources. These islands offer highly fertile lands, forest products, fisheries and other coastal resources. But after a while, the migrants become frustrated finding their habitats overpopulated and eroded. Consequently, they start their bon voyage to newly emerged remote islands. This scenario is very much apparent in *Bhola* and *Noakhali* districts.

How to mitigate?

Preparing environmental risk atlas

The risk atlas will define the vulnerable places and populations facing the most risk from the onset of climate change. This will be developed to identify exposure; vulnerabilities; and risks to populations, ecosystems, biodiversity, supply chains, investments, natural resources and infrastructures. The risk atlas will display hazard, exposure and risk maps. Hazard maps should be available for 12 hazard types: salinity, floods, landslides, mudflows, sedimentation, erosion, drought, water logging, cyclone, windstorm, hailstorm and northwesterly winds.

Ecosystem-based solutions in coastal areas

The Sundarbans comprising of luxuriant biodiversity can accelerate natural resilience to the impacts of climate change by reducing exposure and vulnerability of the poor people. It can stand as a great wall against storm surges. Biodiversity and ecosystem services can be counted as natural capital. This capital can be utilized sustainably to improve livelihoods of the vulnerable people.

Process-based modelling of (agro) forestry in saline area

The proper selection of salt-tolerant trees and crop species can increase the productivity of degraded land. Establishing plantations on highly saline soil with minimal investments can reduce bio-drainage in coastal areas.

Climate resilient livelihoods through community engagements

The involvement of neighbouring people or communities in natural resource management can reduce threats to biodiversity; they would adapt to climate change impacts, and improve livelihoods. Benefits from the ecosystem services and communities' engagements in nature conservation will be mutually exchanged.

Green the blue

From home to a cruise liner there are millions of ways we can keep our water clean and blue. Clean water is the single most important building block of ecosystems around the world. We should go for the green. When we do something, those activities must boost the green as well as our economy. Every single step of an individual should help to solve our social and environmental problems.

Green economy

A green economy focuses on economic growth and employment reducing carbon emissions and pollution, accelerating sustainable development with minimum utilization of natural resources and ecosystem services. Ecosystems or biodiversity finance and natural capital are the two major components of a green economy, which directly evaluates ecological services and treats natural resources as natural capital.

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